

Prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus by Region: Based on the Indonesian Health Survey 2023

D.R. KUSTANTO¹, I.P. Ramadhanti², Y. Armi², M. Fransiska¹, E. Husna³, C.A. Yanti¹, N. Nidianti⁴

¹Universitas Prima Nusantara Bukittinggi, Public Health, Bukittinggi, Indonesia.

²Universitas Prima Nusantara Bukittinggi, Midwifery, Bukittinggi, Indonesia.

³Universitas Prima Nusantara Bukittinggi, Nursing, Bukittinggi, Indonesia.

⁴Universitas Prima Nusantara Bukittinggi, Medicine, Bukittinggi, Indonesia.

Background: Recent projections predict that the global prevalence of diabetes was 9.3% in 2019 and would climb to 10.2% by 2030 and 10.9% by 2045. The Indonesian Ministry of Health reported 10.9% diabetes mellitus prevalence in 2018 and 11.7% in 2023 based on basic health research in 2018 and the Indonesian health survey in 2023.

Objective: The objective of this investigation was to evaluate the prevalence of diabetes mellitus in rural and urban areas of Indonesia based on the location of domicile.

Method: This research employed a cross-sectional design. The study population comprised all Indonesian residents who took part in IHS 2023. The dataset comprised 638,178 individuals aged over 15 years, distributed throughout 38 provinces and 514 districts/cities. The chi-square test was employed to analyse the connection between rural-urban status (independent variable) and diabetes mellitus (dependent variable).

Result: Research indicates that the prevalence of diabetes mellitus in Indonesia stands at 11.7%, with type 2 diabetes mellitus being the most dominant, accounting for 50.1% of cases. The results of the statistical test analysis indicated a significant association between place of residence (rural-urban) and the incidence of diabetes mellitus in Indonesia, with a p-value of less than 0.001 and an odds ratio of 1.794. The analysis indicates that 2.9% of individuals with diabetes mellitus reside in urban areas, while 1.7% are located in rural areas in Indonesia.

Conclusion: The study's findings indicate that the incidence of diabetes mellitus is significantly correlated with the location of domicile (rural-urban), and individuals with diabetes mellitus are more likely to reside in urban areas.